

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and
Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

The first summer school organised
Milestone M5.3

ESiWACE3 Milestone M5.3

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101093054.

Contact details

Project Office: esiwace3@bsc.es

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ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M5.3

Lead Beneficiary:

Sveriges Meteorologiska och Hydrologiska Institut (SMHI), Nikki Brown

Other contributing authors:

CSC-Tieteen Tietotekniikan Keskus OY (CSC), Jarmo Mäkelä

Type:

Dissemination level:

PU (for public use)

Delivery date:

Due in month 21. Actually delivery date: 25th September 2024

Means of verifications:

Web page of the summer school demonstrates that it has been organised.

Achieved:

Yes

If not achieved, indicate forecast achievement date:

-

Comments:

The ESiWACE3-WarmWorld Summer School on HPC for Climate and Weather Applications was held at the Hotelli Korpilampi in Espoo, Finland between 27th August and 2nd September 2024. An invitation and information about the summer school were provided on the ESiWACE3 webpage¹, and registrations were collected through an event page². Seventeen participants attended, and updates about the event were posted on LinkedIn and X (Twitter)⁴.

¹ <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/esiwace3-warmworld-summer-school>

² <https://ssl.eventilla.com/event/1NXdE?t%5BaE3aK%5D=1>

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/esiwace3/>

⁴ <https://x.com/esiwace>

ESiWACE3&WarmWorld Summer School 2024

ESiWACE3-WarmWorld Summer School on HPC for Climate and Weather Applications

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The ESiWACE3-WarmWorld Summer School 2024 aims to bring together young researchers and software engineers interested in the current technological developments in the field of climate modelling. Together, they will explore hot topics in high-performance computing for climate and weather applications.

This Summer School is organised jointly by two projects:

- The [EuroHPC JU CoE ESiWACE3](#), which teams up climate modelling groups and weather services with high-performance computing centres and partners from the IT industry to improve all aspects of the weather and climate modelling workflow;
- And the [German BMBF project WarmWorld](#), which brings together the developers and users of the ICON model to further develop it into a refactored, portable, scalable model delivering km-scale climate projections for the next decades.

 Aug.27.2024 to Sep.02.2024
(Europe/Berlin / UTC200)

 Korpilammentie 5 02970, Espoo Hotelli Korpilampi

 [Visit external website](#)

 [iCal](#)

Venue

This will be an on-site event at the [Hotelli Korpilampi](#) near Helsinki, with no possibility of remote participation. By default, participants will be accommodated in 2-person rooms. However, single rooms may be requested for an added price, but they cannot be guaranteed.

Programme

The participants will attend lectures and practical sessions, guiding them through the fundamentals of performing weather and climate simulations on modern HPC systems and managing and analysing Earth system model data.

At the end of the Summer School, the participants should have:

- Basic understanding of modern climate and weather modelling;
- Practical experience in using climate model output;
- And basic high-performance computing (HPC) skills in weather and climate modelling.

Lecturers

- Cristian-Vasile Achim, CSC
- Claudia Frauen, DKRZ
- Florian Ziemer, DKRZ
- Tuomas Lunttila, CSC
- Jarmo Mäkelä, CSC
- Juha Tonntila, CSC
- Martin Schultz, FZ Jülich
- Victoria Sinclair, University of Helsinki

ESiWACE3 Milestone M5.3

ESiWACE3&WarmWorld Summer School 2024

🕒 27.8.2024 09:00 +03:00 EEST - 2.9.2024 16:00 +03:00 EEST 📍 Hotelli Korpilampi

ESiWACE3-WarmWorld Summer School on HPC for Climate and Weather Applications

27 August - 2 September 2024, Helsinki, Finland

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- Juha Tonttila, CSC
- Martin Schultz, FZ Jülich
- Victoria Sinclair, University of Helsinki

Sessions

- *Block 1: Modeling of weather/climate in the age of HPC and AI*
- *Block 2: ESM data management, evaluation and visualisation*
- *Block 3: MPI, OpenMP, hybrid and GPU programming*
- *Block 4: Novel concepts*

🕒 Event time

Starts: 27.8.2024 09:00 +03:00 EEST
Ends: 2.9.2024 16:00 +03:00 EEST

📍 Event location

Hotelli Korpilampi
Korpilamentie 5
02970 Espoo

[View larger map and directions](#)

The early bird fee for all days is 500 eur + VAT (24 %).

Registration deadline is xx.xx.2024

The fee is all-inclusive. It includes accommodation, four meals and two coffee breaks on most days, social events, course materials, instructed sport activities, and refreshments.

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Participants are expected to have:

- Some basic experience working in a Unix environment;
- Basic knowledge of version control with, e.g. Git;
- And experience with at least one programming language for scientific analysis and visualisation.

There is no need to be an expert in HPC, Unix, or coding to attend the Summer School!

Registration fee: € 500 + VAT (24 %) = € 620

The fee is all-inclusive. It includes accommodation, four meals and two coffee breaks on most days, social events, course materials, instructed sports activities, and refreshments.

Registration Down below!

A copy of the candidate's CV will be required.

Important dates

The registration has two cut-off dates: the early bird deadline and the extended deadline. These dates are put in place to ease participant selection and ensure sufficient quotas for female participants and participants from ITC countries. We will select suitable candidates after each deadline and reserve places for the aforementioned quotas if these have not already been fulfilled. We strongly recommend you apply by the early bird deadline as this will increase your chances of being selected.

- 31 May: Early-bird registration deadline
- 15 June: Extended registration deadline
- 28 June: Confirmation of attendance
- 26 July: Payment deadline
- 27 August - 2 September 2024: Summer School

Contacts

For questions on the Summer School programme:

- [Jarmo Mäkelä](#)
- [Claudia Frauen](#)
- [Elina Plesca](#)

For questions related to the registration process:

- event-support@csc.fi